

In praise of non-standardized collecting: on the wild bee fauna (Hymenoptera: Anthophila) of Greece

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Supplementary material

Supplementary tables legends

Supplementary tables are provided in separated excel files (see zip folder).

Table S1. Dataset used to run the descriptive analyses. The column names follow the Darwin Core Standard, the Pollinator Metadata Standard (Simon Delso *et al.* 2025) and the Pollinator Core template (see Sentil *et al.* 2026). The RDS version of the original database, with script to run the analyses and the metadata file with information on column names and content, are available on the Zenodo repository: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19438412>.

Table S2. Number of genera, species and individuals count organized by family.

Table S3. List of genera, with individuals count and percentage contribution.

Table S4. List of species, with individuals counts.

Table S5. Number of genera, species, and individuals sampled per habitat. Habitats classes, description and major habitat hierarchical level are based on the Corine Land Cover,

Table S6. Matrix with species recorded per habitat classes. Species names are provided in row and habitat classes in column. The number of total individuals per species, and the number of habitat recorded per species is also available.

Supplementary Figures

Figure S1. Example of sampling sites in different Agricultural landscapes in Eastern Macedonia and Crete.

(i) Agricultural areas, class 2.1.1 “Non-irrigated arable land” (credits: Natasha de Manincor)

(ii) Agricultural areas, class 2.2.3 “Olive groves” in Eastern Macedonia and rural path in Olive orchard in Crete (credits: Clément Tourbez, Romain Le Divelec)

(iii) Agricultural areas, class 2.4.2 “Complex cultivation patterns” (credits: Clément Tourbez, Natasha de Manincor)

(iv) Agricultural areas, class 2.4.3 “Land principally occupied by agriculture, with significant areas of natural vegetation” (credits: Natasha de Manincor, Clément Tourbez)

Figure S2. Example of sampling sites in Forest & Seminatural habitats in Eastern Macedonia and Crete.

(i) Forest & Seminatural areas, class 3.1.1 “Broad-leaved forest” (credits: Natasha de Manincor)

(ii) Forest & Seminatural areas, class 3.2.1 “Natural grasslands” in Eastern Macedonia and calcareous grassland in Crete (credits: Natasha de Manincor, Romain Le Divelec)

(iii) Forest & Seminatural areas, class 3.2.3 “Sclerophyllous vegetation” in Crete (credits: Romain Le Divelec)

Figure S3. Example of sampling sites in Artificial habitats in Eastern Macedonia. Artificial surfaces, class 1.1.2 “Discontinuous urban fabric”. Photo credits: Natasha de Manincor.

Figure S4. Example of sampling sites in Wetlands, class 4.2.1 “Salt Marshes”, mainly dominated by *Legousia* sp. flowers. Photo credits: Natasha de Manincor

